

Distrubuted Reseach Data Knowledge Graphs

Challenges of federated queries using Wikidata, Wikibases and the NFDI Knowledge Graph Infrastructure Ecosystem

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Abstract

The emerging ecosystem of distributed research data knowledge graphs (KGs) within the NFDI presents new opportunities—but also profound challenges—for semantic interoperability and federated querying. This contribution explores these challenges through the lens of the Wikiverse (Wikibase, Wikidata) and OpenStreetMap (OSM) as community-driven infrastructures for managing Linked Open Data (LOD), with a focus on their potential as hubs for semantic integration across heterogeneous data domains.

NFDI consortia representing diverse research fields, e.g. NFDI4Objects [1], [2], NFDI4Culture [3], BERD@NFDI [4], NFDI4Society [5], MaRDI [6], and the cross-cutting Base4NFDI—are increasingly investing in distributed KG solutions tailored to their respective research communities. However, diverse modelling paradigms (e.g. RDF vs. LPG), ontological frameworks (e.g. CIDOC CRM vs. BFO or schema.org), and terminological conventions remain significant barriers to integration. The Basic Services TS4NFDI [7] and KG4NFDI [8] address these gaps by offering infrastructure components for terminology alignment and KG federation. This paper contributes to this discourse by evaluating how community-maintained infrastructures—especially Wikibase instances and Wikidata—can support harmonisation efforts and serve as semantic reference points across consortia while raising new issues and challenges in federating the queries.

Drawing on current collaborative experiences from the Knowledge Graph Ecosystem within the NFDI [9], [10], we examine how federated SPARQL queries can be (and cannot be) executed across distributed instances. Federated querying remains technically complex due to inconsistent endpoint configurations, naming conventions, and ontology alignments. These issues are especially pressing in projects using custom Wikibase installations, such as FactGrid, fuzzy-sl, and Semantic Kompakkt. Wikidata

is an important semantic hub for external identifiers, cross-linking with OSM, terminologies, and LOD cloud resources. Its SPARQL endpoint, collaborative curation model, and breadth of scope make it an invaluable resource for interoperable queries across domains.

The contribution highlights how these concepts apply in real-world settings through use cases from NFDI4Objects, NFDI4Culture and MaRDI: (1) Linked Open Ogham, cf. CIIC 81 [11], (Fig. 1 and Fig. 2); (2) Linked Open Samian Ware integrating findspots across LOD repositories [12]; (3) Babylonian mathematics on archaeological objects, e.g., Si.427 [13] (Fig. 3), K08538 [14] or MS 3042 [15]; (4) the Stolpersteine Project explores crowd-sourced volunteered geographic information (VGI) [16] integration; (5) cuneiform tablets made available as 3D scan, LOD in Wikidata and FactGrid [17]. Each example illustrates technical and conceptual hurdles for data federation, such as property mappings, namespace collisions, and endpoint restrictions.

The contribution reflects the sustainability and scalability of current approaches, outlining key lessons learned from recent federation workshops [18] and NFDI-wide coordination efforts [19]. The most promising developments are infrastructure synergies, including services from Base4NFDI, improved query tooling using FAIRification Tools—e.g., SPARQLing Unicorn— and emerging AI-supported ontology alignment and SPARQL query generation methods [20]. By examining the structural complexities and design patterns of distributed semantic infrastructures, we argue that Wikidata and the broader Wikibase ecosystem can play a vital role in bridging disciplinary silos—if adequately supported through community-driven service development and harmonisation efforts.

Keywords: Knowledge Graphs, Wikibase, SPARQL, Federation, Linked Open Data, NFDI, Cultural Heritage, Terminology, Base4NFDI

Figure 3. Known as Si.427, it is the only known example of a cadastral document from this period — a plan used by surveyors to define land boundaries. Obverse of the clay tablet (left) and a sketch of the field on Si.427, with length and area measurements (right). Daniel Mansfield, CC BY-SA 4.0, via Wikimedia Commons.

Resources

- Figure 1. [GitHub:Fig-01](#). “Scheme of Linked Open Ogham within the NFDI Knowledge Graph Ecosystem for visualising a query of the NFDI4Objects Knowledge Graph for Irish Ogham stones, their county and quantity, via <https://t1p.de/v0lg7>, using the SPARQLing Unicorn QGIS Plugin. Florian Thiery, CC BY 4.0.”
- Figure 2. [GitHub:Fig-02](#). “Known as Si.427, it is the only known example of a cadastral document from this period — a plan used by surveyors to define land boundaries. Obverse of the clay tablet (left) and a sketch of the field on Si.427, with length and area measurements (right). Daniel Mansfield, CC BY-SA 4.0, via Wikimedia Commons.”
- Figure 3. [GitHub:Fig-03](#). “Known as Si.427, it is the only known example of a cadastral document from this period — a plan used by surveyors to define land boundaries. Obverse of the clay tablet (left) and a sketch of the field on Si.427, with length and area measurements (right). Daniel Mansfield, CC BY-SA 4.0, via Wikimedia Commons.”
- MSCT 1, 204, MS 3042 (P252052). [P252052](#). “Mathematical tablet excavated in Uncertain (mod. uncertain), dated to the Old Babylonian (ca. 1900-1600 BC) period and now kept in Schøyen Collection, Oslo, Norway.”
- MSCT 1, 219, MS 2192 (P250945). [P250945](#). “Mathematical tablet excavated in Uncertain (mod. uncertain), dated to the Early Old Babylonian (ca. 2000-1900 BC) period and now kept in Schøyen Collection, Oslo, Norway.”
- Si.427. [Si427o.jpg](#) and [Q108028398](#). “Known as Si.427, the ancient clay tablet was discovered and catalogued along with many other tablets by the 1894 French archaeological expedition at Sippar in central Iraq. It’s the only known example of a cadastral document from this period, a plan used by surveyors to define land boundaries.”
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- CIIC 81 3D Model. [CO074-148](#)—. “CIIC 81 / UCC 4 / SMR CO074-148— as 3D model in 3DHOP.”

- SPARQLing Unicorn QGIS Plugin. [GitHub:sparqlunicornGoesGIS](#). “This QGIS plugin adds a Geojson layer from SPARQL endpoint queries.”
- Semantic Kompakt. [GitLab:semantic-kompakkt](#). “Semantic Kompakkt is a free and open source toolchain for the viewing and annotation of 3D models, and other visual media within a linked open data (LOD) environment, via <https://nfdi4culture.de/id/E3752>.”
- Wikibase4Research. [GitLab:wikibase4research](#). “Wikibase4Research is a free and open source suite of tools for the storage and management of Linked Open Data (LOD), via <https://nfdi4culture.de/id/E3759>.”
- archaeology.link. [archaeology.link](#). “ARCHAEOLOGY.LINK presents research data, ontologies, related research tools and web services for e.g., Linked Open Data technologies within the scope of the archaeological basic research carried out by the LEIZA and its cooperation partners in joint projects. This platform complements the LEIZA Archaeological Data Processing Web Service (ADP), via <https://www.nfdi4objects.net/en/portal/services/archaeology-link/>.”
- Wikidata:WikiProject OghamStones. [WikiProject OghamStones](#). “Wikidata Project on Ogham Stones”
- Wikidata:WikiProject Linked Open Samian Ware. [WikiProject LinkedOpenSamianWare](#). “Wikidata Project on Linked Open Samian Ware from the Samian Research Database”
- Wikidata:WikiProject Stolpersteine. [WikiProject Stolpersteine](#). “Wikidata Project on the Stolpersteine”
- DE:Stolpersteine. [OSM-DE:Stolpersteine](#). “Information for modelling Stolpersteine on Open Street Map.”

Author contributions

This section uses the abbreviations of the author names. Conceptualization: FT, LR, DM; Data curation: FT, LR, DM, TH, PT; Formal analysis: FT, LR, DM, TH; Investigation: FT, LR, DM, TH; Methodology: FT, LR, DM, TH; Resources: FT, LR, DM, TH, PT; Software: FT, LR, DM, TH; Visualization: FT, LR, DM; Writing – original draft: FT, LR, DM; Writing – review & editing: FT, LR, DM.

Competing interests

The authors declare that they have no competing interests.

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